

NUTRITIONAL CONTENT OF MULBERRY LEAVES AND JUICINESS OF THE FRUIT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7786286>

Abstract. *The purpose of this work is to restore human health through the analysis of the leaves and fruits of the mulberry tree, the study of The Silkworm's nutrient base and natural treatment with the help of Mulberry fruits.*

Keywords: *mulberry, mulberry leaf, cocoon, boiling point, tincture, blood pressure, blood sugar level, dried mulberry, silkworm, nutrient content, amino acids, biophysical traps.*

I. Introduction

Mulberry is one of the most hardy trees that requires very little maintenance. It is known for its juicy, fragrant fruits. China used these leaves to feed silkworms. As a result, the mulberry tree became an important part of the Chinese silk trade. Today we use the leaves in other ways, mainly for food additives and tea leaves. There are three types of mulberry trees – red, white and black. They are named for the color of the fruit. The leaves are very similar with small differences. The benefits of mulberry leaves due to the beneficial properties of mulberry leaves are used in traditional Asian medicine. Most of them have been proven in clinical trials. The main benefits of mulberry leaves are mulberry tree used in traditional Asian medicine to treat diabetes. Therefore, its effectiveness was confirmed in scientific tests. A 2017 study published on PLoS ONE found that mulberry leaf extract is rich in carbohydrates after eating blood glucose II.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Improve heart health many studies have shown that mulberry leaves can be beneficial for our cardiovascular health. A 2018 study published in the journal *Pharmaceutical Biology* concluded that phenols and flavonoids present in leaves reduce cardiometabolic risks. Another study published in *BioMed Research International* found that these antioxidants work by lowering serum triglycerides, CRP, and LDL levels. [2] [3] it can help reduce obesity mulberry tree leaves have had a great impact in the fight against weight loss and obesity. An animal study published in the *Journal of Experimental Biology and Medicine* showed that mulberry leaf extract works in several channels by reducing obesity and associated complications. This includes improving plasma triglycerides, adipocyte size, lipid peroxidation levels in the liver, and hepatic steatosis. [4] Reducing the risk of chronic diseases the anti-inflammatory properties of Tut are explained by its ability to reduce the risk of chronic diseases. A study published in *Functional Foods* found that mulberry leaf extract helps reduce the effects of inflammatory compounds such as cytokines. This extract can be very effective against chronic conditions and inflammations such as arthritis,

fibrosis, diabetes and cancer. Studies have shown that mulberry extract is dose-dependent, since it is based on a dosage regimen, home alternatives such as mulberry tea can help achieve similar results. [5] chemoprophylaxis potential mulberry leaves have long been considered useful in traditional Chinese medicine for the treatment of chronic diseases. A review published in the Journal of traditional and complementary medicine contains a variety of studies of mulberry extract (including clinical and laboratory tests).

The study found that Mulberry helps in the prevention and treatment of various cancers. To create a better immunity in the East, it is recommended to combine it with drugs. [6] the use of mulberry leaves the leaves of Mulberry are the only food source of silkworms. But they also have a lot to do.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

As mentioned above, mulberry leaves have been used in Asian cultures for centuries due to their healing properties. They are also used for food purposes. Young delicate leaves can be prepared and eaten. You can use it instead of grape leaves in the preparation of caviar tak according to the recipe. It is often used as a food additive in the United States. Another popular way to use mulberry leaves is to brew dried leaves in tea. How to make tea from mulberry leaves? Mulberry leaf tea is very easy to prepare. You just need to brew tea leaves or tea bags in hot water. Tea is made from dried leaves. In the US, you can buy tea from certified plants or order it online. You can easily get tea bags from mulberry leaves. When buying tea, we recommend that you look for organic brands. Tea from mulberry leaves has a light bitter sweet taste. Tea leaves are very easy to prepare by brewing them in hot water. Cooking time: 3 minutes brewing time: 5 minutes preparation 1 teaspoon mulberry tea leaves per 1 cup of boil or, 1 tea bag from mulberry tree leaves, 1 cup filtered water, honey or lemon optionally.

1. Mulberry tea is best brewed with water at a boiling temperature of 160-200 degrees. To do this, boil a glass of water. Let it cool for a minute.

2. Add tea leaves to the kettle and pour hot water. You can also brew a tea bag in a glass of hot water.

3. Let the tea leaves brew for 3-5 minutes. If using a teapot, put the tea in a cup. Your tea is ready! Tea from mulberry leaves is usually taken without additives. However, you can add honey or lemon if desired. If the tea seems too strong to you, try to brew it less the next time. Keep in mind that if you dip it in hot water several times, the tea bag will take less time. Recently appeared

in the American landscape. But it is becoming more and more popular, the leaves of the mulberry tree do not have a single shape even on one tree. Mulberry leaves are heart-shaped or oval with edges and edges. The leaves often have deep blades, the mulberry leaves are rarely symmetrical, the texture can vary slightly between different types of Mulberry. Although it has been part of traditional Chinese medicine for centuries, we do not have long-term studies on the bad effects of mulberry leaves or drinking tea from it. Therefore, we advise you to be careful when taking this tea. Pregnant women and children should avoid drinking tea because there have been no long-term studies on its safety. It should also be borne in mind that mulberry leaves are known to reduce blood sugar. As always, if you are taking any medication, talk to your doctor before including it in your diet. The benefits of mulberry leaf are the same as the positive health effects of Mulberry. The most important advantage of Mulberry fruits is the antipyretic effect. To do this, eat Mulberry. Tea made from the leaves of a mulberry tree has the same effect. Scientific evidence from research at leading medical institutions in the United States, India, France and Asia proves the miracle of the mulberry tree. Dr. Ibrahim Sarajoglu, Dr. Feridun kunak (doctor of Turkish medicinal plants), like experts, talks about the benefits of the leaves of this plant in many places.

IV. Results

The benefits of mulberry leaves are as follows

№	Useful effect of tincture
1	Controls blood pressure and blood sugar
2	Mulberry leaves are a very important factor in the treatment of diabetes
3	Lowers cholesterol to a minimum
4	It is a herb commonly used by liver patients
5	It contains antioxidant substances and helps to remove tumors
6	Mulberry and mulberry leaves, which are used in heart disease, balance rhythm disturbances in the heart, tighten and cleanse the intestines
7	Mulberry fruit and mulberry leaves are very rich in amino acids
8	Calcium, potassium, magnesium, iron and zinc from the point of view of a very rich plant
9	Used in the treatment of bone diseases and bone strengthening
10	Regulates the digestive system, promotes constipation
11	Mulberry Tree Hair Benefits up to the following benefits mulberry leaves are very rich in magnesium, iron and calcium
12	For healthy hair, iron intake should be adequate and balanced. For this reason, mulberry leaves are very useful for a healthy and strong hair structure.
13	The benefits of mulberry leaves for the liver are as follows with the regular use of dry and fresh mulberry leaves they especially protect against liver cancer
14	In addition, it is effective against dumbbells

When to harvest the leaves of a mulberry tree, the timing of harvesting mulberry leaves is very important. As a result of all scientific research, it should be understood that the leaves should be harvested immediately before ripening early spring mulberry leaves should be collected in green. Then the leaves can lose their nutritional value and even become poisonous. To dry mulberry leaves, all fresh vegetables and fruits are dried in the sun at the hottest time. It should be remembered that in places where the fruit is too hot in the direct sun, vegetables can be harmful. Therefore, it should be dried in the ground in the shade, close to the sun. Mulberry leaves can be

eaten fresh and dried. In the same way, you can brew fresh and dried tea, boil fresh mulberry leaves and eat them in the form of a salad. To make tea from fresh mulberry leaves, you must first wash them very well. Take the powder, put the leaves in boiling water and bring to a boil. Then you can eat it. Preparation of dry mulberry tea 1.2 tablespoons of dried mulberry, 2. 4 cups of cold water, a teaspoon of honey to taste, if desired, you can make tea from dry mulberry leaves. Over low heat for 4-10 minutes. Then take it out of the oven. Dry mulberry leaves benefits for human skin mulberry leaves dry, eczema, redness, etc. are very important in the treatment of all skin diseases. Like dried leaves, it has properties that restore the skin, as it has the maximum level of antioxidants. There are several treatments for hair loss. Mulberry leaves are very useful even when they are dry and fresh. Mulberry fresh leaves are very difficult to store, they are kept dry. The use of the leaves of the mulberry tree their leaves are used for several diseases. Compared to black and red, white mulberry leaves (*Morus alba*) are economically more expensive to grow silkworm. In fact, a few years ago, the extensive cultivation of these trees contributed to the development of the silk industry. Today, more than 700 varieties of Mulberry are grown in Japan. Because it is a very hardy flowering plant, farmers have less energy to grow and grow it. Another advantage is the high yield of leaves and fruits with minimal care and care. If a farmer grows mulberry trees to grow silkworms, he can also raise fish, ducks, pigs, and goats. In some regions, thin leaves are eaten as a nutritious vegetable. When collecting leaves and other green teas [7,8]

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The mulberry tree has been revered for many years for its fragrant fruits and nutritious leaves. Although the berries are tasty and rich in many nutrients, the leaves are good for health. What are the leaves of the mulberry tree? The mulberry tree is native to Asia, but is now found in many countries around the world. Mulberry leaves have been used for centuries due to their healing properties, culinary benefits and excellent nutritional composition. Traditionally, it was used to make tea or cooked and added to food. Mulberry leaves do not contain caffeine and tannins. Currently, it is widely used in food additives. The nutritional properties of mulberry leaves are responsible for its health benefits. In addition to the nutrients described above, the leaves also include: [9]

№	Types of vitamins scale of beneficial effect	Types of vitamins scale of beneficial effect
1	A	Essential vitamin for vision and immunity
2	B ₁	For healthy skin, muscles, immunity and nervous system
3	B ₂	For stomach and muscle function
4	B ₆	Essential for nerve function and protein metabolism
5	S	Vitamin is a powerful antioxidant with many important functions in the body

6	Amino acid protein depletion	Amino acid protein depletion
	Calcium for weak bones	Calcium for weak bones

It can be seen from this that it is of great importance to ensure the protection of the mulberry tree from various pest insects, since mulberry leaf is a medicinal plant that benefits not only for the cultivation of sawdust, for the health of humans *kyeltruvch*. The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on additional measures for the development of The Silkworm feed base in the sawmilling network dated 17.01.2020. PQ-4567 No. 1-2, Article 7. In this decision of the president, the fact that the *tutzors* are one of the current *dolbzar* issues is in the sawmills, and the further development of the economy of Medicine will have a good economic effect in the prosperous, healthy living of our people. The application of biophysical grips used for sunning is significant in eliminating the enormous damage.

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